

**COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF DIFFERENT METHODS FOR DETECTING
BRAIN TUMOR BY USING MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGES****Khushboo Vishwakarma**Khushboo.vishwakarma2001@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

A brain tumor impairs the body's ability to operate normally and poses a threat to life. Early brain tumor detection is essential for an accurate diagnosis and effective treatment planning because diagnosis is challenging, particularly in the early stages of the illness. Conventional methods frequently shorten patients' lives by delaying the necessary medical care. Because the appearance of tumor tissues varies greatly among patients and frequently resembles normal tissues, automating this process is a difficult undertaking. MRI is a sophisticated medical imaging method that offers a wealth of data regarding the soft-tissue anatomy of humans. In the past, several academics have suggested semi-automated and completely automated techniques for identifying and classifying brain tumors in this article. Thus, this paper analyzed the literature in a streamlined manner and concentrated on the work of numerous scholars. The main objective of this work is to provide a comprehensive critical analysis of these studies and findings made in the recent past to detect and classify brain cancers using MRI scans. Researchers that specialize in deep learning, machine learning technologies, neural network etc and wish to use their knowledge to detect and categorize brain tumors will particularly benefit from this investigation.

Keywords:

Brain Tumor, MRI-Images, Fuzzy Means, Morphological Operators, ML Techniques

INTRODUCTION

One of the most-deadly brain diseases is brain tumors, which are caused by aberrant tissue growth inside the skull. We are defining two tumors: first one is primary and 2nd is secondary. While secondary brain cancers start in other organs like the breast, kidney, or lung before spreading to the brain, primary brain tumors, which make up 70% of cases [3], exclusively spread within the brain. The expansion rate of the brain tumor among kids and adults are growing exponentially daily. Therefore swift and precise detection of the brain tumor can be extremely beneficial to keep up a wholesome way of life. Brain tumors must be identified and diagnosed early in order to be adequately prevented. However, even in fields as complex as medicine, artificial intelligence (AI) has expanded rapidly [11]. A framework for investigating cutting-edge deep learning architectures for the classification and detection of brain tumors is put forth here.

Medical image data from various biomedical equipment that use various imaging techniques, such as MRI, CT scan, and X-ray [1], is a crucial component in medical diagnosis. The technology known as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) relies on measuring the magnetic field vectors that are produced in the nuclei of hydrogen atoms found in a patient's body's water molecules following the proper excitation of strong magnetic fields and radio frequency pulses.

Since MRI scans don't involve radiation, they are far superior to CT scans for diagnosis. MRI allows radiologists to assess the brain. The presence of a brain tumor can be detected using the MRI technology.

Human examination is the traditional technique for detecting tumors in MRI images. This approach takes a lot of time[8]. It is not favorable for huge data sets. Additionally, operator-induced noise in the MRI can result in incorrect classification. Since automated systems are more economical, they are required for the analysis of large volumes of MRI data. Since dealing with human life requires a high level of accuracy, automated tumor detection in MRI images is required.

Fig 1: MRI Images of Brain

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI): The process of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) creates images of the body by polarizing and exciting hydrogen nuclei, such as the proton in water molecules in human tissue, using strong magnets. This produces a detectable signal that is spatially recorded. Three electromagnetic fields are primarily used in MRIs, and they are: i) A weaker time-varying field or fields for spatial encoding, known as the gradient field; ii) A extremely powerful static magnetic field, or "static field," to polarize the hydrogen nuclei; and iii) To control hydrogen nuclei and produce measurable signals that RF antennas can detect, a weak radio frequency field is used. The appearance of different tissues is caused by the diverse ways that protons behave within them.

The following are this study's primary contributions:

- An analysis of different methods for classifying brain tumors using unique deep learning models that include thorough preprocessing, transfer learning architectural change, and efficiency-boosting fine-tuning [15].
- The reconfiguration architecture is altered to use the GPU speed and address overfitting issues by incorporating images. Additionally, the attempt to complement the augmentation process is aided by the ability to instantly standardize photos based on the configuration [19].
- Adding layers using the altered design that enables us to create a new deep learning architecture for effectively classifying brain tumors is known as fine-tuning.
- Lastly, determine the optimal model to classify brain tumors by evaluating the performance of our suggested models based on a number of factors, such as accuracy, precision, recall, f1-score, and confusion matrix [9].

RELATED WORK

The ultimate goal of using various imaging techniques is to extract valuable information from a given image. Medical professionals execute the crucial yet time-consuming task of segmenting brain tumors from magnetic resonance scans [18]. Numerous segmentation techniques, many of which are ad hoc, have been developed by the digital image processing community.

The first 4 steps of the four most widely used methods are region-growing segmentation, template matching, texture segmentation, and amplitude thresholding.[17].

These kinds of techniques are employed to classify the brain images into three groups: (a) based on pixels; (b) based on regions or textures; and (c) based on structures. The necessary data is extracted based on the region that was retrieved.

Fig 2 Stages involved in Brain Tumor Detection

Image Acquisition: Images are acquired by MRI scans of the brain, which produce grayscale images as their output. A data matrix with values representing shades of gray is called a grayscale image[17]. The grayscale matrix's elements have intensity values or integer values between 0 and 255. The MRI digital pictures are saved in matrix form for use with various procedures.

Noise Removal: In image processing, there are many different types of filters that can be used to eliminate noise, and each filter has unique properties. Spatial noise filters are used in this techniques are employed to eliminate noise. Filters are generally categorized into two types based on their behavior and design: linear and non-linear filters.

Image Enhancement: Enhancement will make the edges more noticeable and provide a sharper image. It will also minimize noise, which will lessen the image's blurring effect. This enlarged and improved image will aid in edge detection and raise the overall image quality[16].

Converting gray to binary: A binary image is a logical array of white (one) and black (zero) values. The toolbox function i.e im2bw converts the grayscale images into binary format very effectively. The input data's entire range is scaled to fall between 0 and 1. The threshold idea is used in this approach. The threshold concept functions by choosing a specific threshold value, T , to distinguish between different data classes.

Morphological Operators: A technique for extracting image elements, such as boundaries, skeletons, etc., that are helpful in the representation and description of region shape is known as mathematical morphology

Two basic morphological operations are as follows: dilatation and erosion, respectively. These are described by the union and intersection of a translated form, known as a structural element, with an image.

Edge Detection: Finding the tumor's edges is the final stage. This phase can sometimes be skipped because morphological operators are used to detect the tumor. However, the precise outcome is achieved using edge detection.

Morphological Watershed Segmentation: Three main ideas form the basis of image segmentation: Region processing, thresholding, and discontinuity detection are the first three steps. Many of the ideas of the three methods mentioned above are embodied in Morphological Watershed Image Segmentation. More stable segmentation, including continuous segmentation boundaries, is frequently the result. Watershed is usually used for output testing rather than as an input segmentation technique because it usually suffers from both over and under segmentation.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Using MR images, numerous researchers have proposed numerous techniques and algorithms to detect brain tumors, strokes, and other types of abnormalities in the human brain. This section covered current techniques for classifying and segmenting brain tumors using MRI images [12]. Based on prior subject expertise, the

traditional clinical method for segmenting brain disorders is manual. Manual segmentation is time consuming and often leads in error at accuracy of classification.

Over the years, academics have put forth a number of automated methods to overcome these issues. The segmentation and classification methods based on deep learning approaches, regular machine learning techniques, and metaheuristic algorithms in recent years are the main subject of this paper's analytical review.

In 2019 Javaria Amin, Muhammad Sharif and his team proposed a method for detecting brain tumors with statistical and machine learning methods. The input slices are enhanced and de-noised using a Weiner filter with several wavelet bands. Potential Field (PF) clustering is used to identify subsets of tumor pixels. Additionally, the tumor site is isolated in Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (Flair) and T2 MRI using global threshold and several mathematical morphological methods. Gabor Wavelet Transform (GWT) and Local Binary Pattern (LBP) are combined for precise and accurate feature categorization. The final result of their experiments on a local dataset, the method produced 0.010 ER and 0.93 FG and 0.98 BG precision. The multimodal brain tumor segmentation challenge dataset BRATS 2013 yields a precision of 0.93 FG and 0.99 BG and 0.005 ER [4].

V. Sivakumar & N. Janakiraman at 2020, suggested three stages of work they are segmentation, edge detection, and preprocessing. The MRI images are first taken out of the database, and a high pass filter is applied to each input image to improve it. After preprocessing, the image is enhanced using the Enhanced Canny Edge Detection (ECED) technique. The Modified Watershed Segmentation (MWS) technique is used for additional segmentation once the Region of Interest (ROI) has been extracted from the MRI image. The results of the tests show that the suggested system performs well in comparison to the existing solutions. The implementation is carried out using the Xilinx Virtex-5 Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA). [12]

In 2020, Sepehr Salem Ghahfarrokhi & Hamed Khodadadi they resolve complexity measurements like the Lyapunov Exponent (LE), Approximate Entropy (ApEn), and Fractal Dimension (FD) are estimated using the chaos theory. Benign and malignant tumors can also be distinguished by extracting features using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) techniques. Three classifiers, including the Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm, and pattern net, are subjected to the computed features. Several tests are conducted on the different feature and classifier combinations throughout the validation phase. As a result, combining complexity measures with GLCM features and pattern net classifier yields the highest accuracy (98.9%). Additionally, the effectiveness of the suggested approach is demonstrated by comparing the findings of this study with those of other comparable studies using the same dataset.[1]

Anish Vijana, Parth Dubeya, and Shruti Jain, proposed the comparative analysis of various image fusion techniques for Brain tumor i.e Fusion approaches include multimodality (MM). Computed Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) scans are among the modalities that are fused in MM. Each modality has unique features, including complimentary anatomy and different kinds of functional information.

MRI and CT scans are frequently used to detect brain tumors and strokes. This study combines T1 weighted (T1), T1 contrast enhancing (T1ce), T2weighted (T2), and Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (Flair) slices of a patient's brain MR images to diagnose abnormalities and brain pathology. Principle Component Analysis (PCA) fusion techniques, the Laplacian Pyramid Transform methodology, and the Discrete Wavelet transform (DWT) were used in a number of experiments.[6]

Zahraa A. Al-Saffar & Tülay Yildirim defined a hybrid approach which describes study has looked into a number of techniques to enhance the results and lessen the difficulties associated with medical picture analysis. Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) based brain tumor classification are among them, as are Local Difference in Intensity-Means (LDI-Means) based brain tumor segmentation, Mutual Information (MI) based feature selection, and Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) based dimensionality reduction. Additionally, a novel technique called Multiple Eigenvalues Selection (MES) was introduced in this study to select the most significant characteristics to use as classifier inputs. By the combination of supervised and unsupervised methods, makes an efficient system for brain glioma grading. The suggested strategy performed exceptionally well in terms of accuracy, recall, specificity, precision, and error rate, according to the experimental data. They are, in order, 91.02%, 86.52%, 94.26%, 87.07%, and 0.0897. [2]

Raphael M. Kronberg and his team aimed to segment necrotic core, peritumoral edema, and augmenting tumor using the Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2018 winner algorithm, which was trained on the BraTS 2020 dataset. Using the Dice score (DS) as the main criterion, we compared the segmentation performance for every

possible combination of sequences. We contrast the outcomes with those that would be attained by making an effort to adhere to the consensus guidelines for imaging brain tumors [T1, FLAIR, T2, T1CE]. The average segmentation accuracy ranges from 0.751 for the entire collection of sequences to 0.476 for T1 alone. T1CE gave a substantial information that even regarding the peritumoral edema, while T2 and FLAIR will offer mostly a redundant data. [5]

Sakshi Ahuja and its team proposed brain tumor classification, localization, and segmentation from T1W-CE Magnetic Resonance Image (MRI) datasets are the goals of the proposed work. Eighty percent of the T1W-CE MRI dataset is used for training, ten percent for each validation, and ten percent for testing. Geometrical operations (scaling, rotation, translation) and 2-level wavelet decomposition are used to enhance the training data set in order to overcome the overfitting problems. The effectiveness of pre-trained DarkNet models (DarkNet-19 and DarkNet-53) is assessed for brain tumor location and multi-class categorization. The top-performing pre-trained DarkNet model had a training accuracy of 99.60% and a validation accuracy of 98.81%. [7]

Priyanka C. Nair along others The model makes use of classifiers that can naturally manage missing data, such as XGBoost, Local Cascade Ensemble, Histogram-based gradient boosting, LightGBM, and CatBoost. Even though machine learning models are good at categorization, their interpretability and generalizability are frequently questioned, particularly in crucial fields like healthcare and medicine. The ELIS tool, a Python package for explainable AI, has therefore been used to examine model performance. This tool gives clinicians a more interpretable model by identifying the important characteristics in the data on a patient-by-patient basis [13].

Md. Monirul Islam team purpose of their project is to determine how well deep transfer learning architectures diagnose brain tumors. Their study employs four transfer learning architectures: InceptionV3, VGG19, DenseNet121, and MobileNet. To validate the models, we used a dataset that included information from three benchmark databases: Br35H, SARTAJ, and figshare. Their databases had included four categories: glioma, meningioma, pituitary tumor, and no tumor. To balance the classes, image augmentation is used. Results from experiments show that MobileNet performs better than competing techniques, with an accuracy of 99.60%. [14]

METHODOLOGY

This paper provides a comparative analysis of different approaches used in Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) brain tumor detection and classification. Traditional machine learning, deep learning, hybrid approaches, and sophisticated image processing techniques are among the strategies taken into consideration. The chosen methods' accuracy on both public and private datasets, preprocessing approaches, and segmentation/classification capabilities have all been evaluated.

Fig 3 Workflow of Brain Tumor Detection

The above figure defines the workflow of brain tumor detection using MRI images to detect brain tumors is depicted in the diagram. It involves the following procedures in order: MRI scan acquisition, pre-processing, tumor region segmentation, feature extraction, image analysis, and diagnosis. For efficient clinical decision-making, this methodical technique improves brain tumor identification accuracy and efficiency.

4.1 Research Approach

The study's analytical approach is founded on a thorough analysis of the methods currently used to detect brain tumors. Several well-known models and techniques put forth by more recent academics are evaluated using the comparative framework, with an emphasis on their implementation pipelines, feature extraction techniques, classifier types, and published results.

4.2 Sources of Data

The study mostly concentrates on research that used common MRI datasets, such as:

- BRATS (2013–2020): For the segmentation and classification of multimodal brain tumors.
- Local hospital datasets: Used for validation in previous studies.
- Open repositories such as SARTAJ, Br35H, and Figshare.
- Various MRI slice types, such as T1, T1CE, T2, and FLAIR, were used; depending on the approach, these slices were frequently merged or examined separately.

4.3 Techniques for Image Preprocessing

The majority of techniques which was used in preprocessing to improve MRI image quality:

- Filtering and Enhancement: To reduce noise and improve brain pictures, Wiener filter and high-pass filtering were used (e.g., Amin et al., 2019; Sivakumar et al., 2020).
- Edge Detection and Segmentation: Tumor boundaries were defined using methods such as Modified Watershed Segmentation and Enhanced Canny Edge Detection.
- Image Fusion: To integrate structural and functional information, the T1, T1CE, T2, and FLAIR slices were fused using PCA, DWT, or Laplacian Pyramid techniques.

4.4 Methods of Classification and Segmentation

A variety of techniques were examined and divided into the following groups:

A. Conventional Methods for Machine Learning

- Texture and Statistical Features: extracted using GLCM, Local Binary Patterns (LBP), and Gabor Wavelet Transform (GWT).
- Feature Reduction: Dimensionality was decreased by employing techniques such as SVD and MI.
- Classifiers: On engineered features, SVM, KNN, and Pattern Net classifiers were used (e.g., Ghahfarrokhi et al., 2020).

B. Models for Deep Learning

- CNN-based architectures: For tumor classification and localization, Deep CNNs such as DarkNet-19, DarkNet-53, DenseNet121, and VGG19 were employed (e.g., Ahuja et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2020).
- Transfer Learning: To increase accuracy and cut down on training time, pre-trained models (such as MobileNet and InceptionV3) were refined on datasets of brain tumors.

C. Advanced and Hybrid Methods

- Combination of Unsupervised and Supervised learning: To increase its precision, efficiency, accuracy, feature selection techniques like MES and MI were integrated with SVM, MLP, and LD-Intensity Means (e.g., Al-Saffar et al.)
- Model Explainability: The ELI5 tool for model interpretability was used to examine tree-based ensemble models such as XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM (e.g., Nair et al.)

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this paper is comprehensive analysis of the literature on the development of brain tumor segmentation in the context of deep learning and federated learning during the previous few decades. Common approaches, such as ensembles, multimodality, cascaded networks, and pre-trained models, are compiled after a careful review of the body of current literature. CNN and its numerous structures and uses in medical imaging were the main focus.

The following is a summary of the main conclusions of this review.

1. Although there are several segmentation methods for brain tumors, cascaded networks outperform other methods in terms of tumor detection due to their ability to extract the most features. Furthermore, ensembling approaches work better for precise segmentation that produces results that are balanced.
2. Combining data from many sources can facilitate communication and broaden the scope of features. Agregation or inclusion does not demonstrate how features are used, nor does it introduce new parameters. Using a small network, an attention method can maximize feature expression, additional parameters and raise computing costs.
3. Invariant feature extraction helps retrieve relevant information from the available modality data when some modalities are missing.

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